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To cite this article: Dominik Petko, Konstantinos Michos, Laura Müller, Regina Schmid & Maike Krannich (16 Oct 2024): Investigating the use of a mobile portfolio app to develop pre-service teachers' reflective abilities and orientations to learning to teach, European Journal of Teacher Education, DOI: [10.1080/02619768.2024.2414912](https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2024.2414912)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2024.2414912>

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Published online: 16 Oct 2024.

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Investigating the use of a mobile portfolio app to develop pre-service teachers' reflective abilities and orientations to learning to teach

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ABSTRACT

Mobile technologies are expected to provide many benefits for teacher reflection during teaching practice. However, empirical studies on these outcomes are still scarce. In an experimental field trial, we tested the effects of different variants of a mobile portfolio app on the development of pre-service teachers' self-reported reflective ability, their orientations to learning to teach (e.g. developing ideas through discussion), and the interaction between their use of the mobile portfolio and orientation with regard to the development of reflective ability. Although there were only small direct effects of using the mobile app to foster reflective ability, the use of the app seemed to enhance the willingness to develop ideas for teaching practice through discussion and communication with mentors. These orientations were positively correlated with reflective ability; however, they showed no moderating effect on reflective ability when using the app.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 5 May 2022
Accepted 4 October 2024

KEYWORDS

Teaching practice; reflection; orientations; eportfolio; mobile learning

Introduction

In recent years, digital technologies have offered new pathways to foster teacher education and professional development (Feder and Cramer 2019; Kori et al. 2014; Romano and Schwartz 2005). These digital technologies include digital videos, e-portfolios, weblogs, social media applications, and mobile apps. Research on mobile apps for teachers' education is still in its infancy, and evidence on the fundamental effects of their professional development is lacking. Therefore, we investigated the effects of a mobile portfolio app on pre-service teachers' reflective abilities and related learning and regulation activities. Our study analysed the isolated effects and interplay of these factors by comparing different variants of the app. The theoretical background of this study is detailed in the following sections.

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Fostering teachers' reflection and reflective abilities

Reflection is one of the core concepts of professional development in many disciplines (Lyons 2010; Moon 1999) and especially in teacher education (Darling-Hammond and Richardson 2009; Fendler 2003; Korthagen, Loughran, and Russell 2006). Reflection serves as one of the key activities bridging the gap between theory and practice and has been one of the biggest challenges in teacher education throughout the last century (Dewey 1904; Shulman 1998). Numerous studies have reported that reflection on teaching practice often remains shallow, as student teachers often provide superficial descriptions, personal impressions, and spontaneous ideas when reflecting on teaching situations rather than concept-driven analyses and strategic adjustments (Beauchamp 2015; Dymont and O'Connell 2010; Marcos, Miguel, and Tillema 2009). Although pre-service teachers often regard their internship experiences as prime learning opportunities, teaching internships do not always yield the intended results (Burn and Mutton 2015; Cohen, Hoz, and Kaplan 2013; Hascher 2012; Wideen, Mayer-Smith, and Moon 1998). Even when pre-service teachers are knowledgeable in relevant pedagogical theories and concepts, they do not necessarily put their knowledge into practice, either because such knowledge is 'idle knowledge' of 'knowing that' rather than 'knowing how', or because it does not comply with their motivational dispositions or beliefs (Blömeke et al. 2008). Another common challenge of school internships and practical teaching experiences during teacher education is avoiding pre-service teachers simply adopting questionable behaviours and routines modelled by senior teachers (e.g. Korthagen and Kessels 1999; Schüpbach 2007; Zeichner and Tabachnick 1981). Even if teachers engage in reflection, research has struggled to show consistent effects of pre-service teachers' reflective practice on actual professional development (Bakkenes, Vermunt, and Wubbels 2010; Roessger 2014; Van Beveren et al. 2018). Nevertheless, high-quality reflection on pre-service teachers' own classroom practices, in particular with guidance from experienced teachers and university mentors, has remained the core approach of most teacher education programmes (Darling-Hammond and Richardson 2009; Hiebert 1999; Lipowski 2011; Maksimović and Osmanović 2018; Roffey-Barentsen and Malthouse 2009). To empower meaningful reflection and reflective practice, pre-service teachers need to engage in adequate learning and self-regulation activities. In this context, productive 'orientations toward learning to teach' have been described and investigated by Oosterheert, Vermunt, and Denessen (2002), distinguishing four types of learning activities that might foster reflection and professional development: actively seeking input from the teacher education mentor, discussing ideas with more experienced teachers, actively relating theory and practice, and reflecting one's teaching against student-oriented evaluation criteria. Although previous studies show evidence on pre-service teachers' orientations towards learning to teach change during internships (Endedijk, Donche, and Oosterheert 2013; Goller et al. 2020), studies on the use of digital technologies and mobile portfolios to develop these orientations are lacking.

Mobile technologies as tools for teacher reflection

Before digital technologies became pervasive, paper-based teaching plans, field notes, reflective journals, and teaching portfolios were employed to stimulate

and interact with reflection-on-action during field experiences (Zeichner 1987). In recent years, tools for reflection have moved beyond paper-based approaches to embrace digital technologies, using video (Gaudin and Chaliès 2015; Hamel, Viau-Guay, and Nkuyubwatsi 2019; Prilop, Weber, and Kleinknecht 2019), weblogs (Petko, Egger, and Cantieni 2017; Sim and Hew 2010; Wopereis, Sloep, and Poortman 2010), e-portfolios (Feder and Cramer 2019; Karsenti, Dumouchel, and Collin 2014; Strudler and Wetzel 2005), or social media applications for the purposes of teacher education (Archambault et al. 2010; Greenhow et al. 2018; Iredale et al. 2019; Prestridge 2019).

In contrast to their traditional counterparts, digital technologies include new elements, such as multimedia records (e.g. audio and video), hyperlinks (e.g. crosslinks, tags), and new forms of online access, as well as synchronous and asynchronous communication (e.g. comments, likes). Next to desktop-based applications, an especially promising approach is the use of mobile technologies for the documentation of notable moments that serve as a trigger of posterior reflection in teacher education (Baran 2014; Garcia-Martinez et al. 2019; Leinonen et al. 2014; Seppälä and Alamäki 2003). Mobile technologies facilitate the collection of records in practical situations where the use of desktop computers is not possible or might be disturbing. Mobile apps enable situated note-taking, capturing pictures, and recording audio or videos. Thus, thoughts and reflection processes can be directly linked to specific practical situations (Sophonhiranrak 2021). This kind of microblogging via mobile apps allows for reflection-in-action, whereas blogging or traditional (retrospective) journal writing focuses on reflection-on-action (Moon 2006; Schön 1983). In particular, recording notable moments-in-action can foster pre-service teachers' abilities for professional noticing and the perception and interpretation of critical classroom situations (Blömeke, Gustafsson, and Shavelson 2015; Hadjistassou and Allen 2018). Thus, mobile apps support pre-service teachers' in developing a 'professional vision' which has been identified as an important prerequisite for teachers' effective teaching (Depaepe, Verschaffel, and Star 2020; Goodwin 1994; Lachner, Jarodzka, and Nückles 2016; Seidel and Stürmer 2014). Although several studies have shown that pre-service teachers successfully develop their reflective ability with eportfolios (Dune et al. 2018; Kelly 2010), findings regarding the specific affordances of mobile portfolios are still lacking.

Another aim of using digital technologies, such as weblogs, microblogs, and digital portfolios, in teacher education is to strengthen the social context of reflection. Studies show that communication with peers and tutors increases with the use of digital tools, and this helps alleviate feelings of loneliness in remote placement sites (Dickey 2004; Hramiak, Boulton, and Irwin 2009). The perceived sense of community is among the strongest predictors of perceived learning gains (Top, Yukselturk, and Inan 2010). The communicative aspect of digital record keeping and reflection was found to be further intensified through microblogging, in which informal exchanges seemed to foster communities of practice over time (Ebner et al. 2010; Krutka et al. 2014; Wright 2010). Regarding more formal settings, the process of reflective writing has often been found to require specific writing tasks, prompts, scripts, scaffolds, and feedback to be successful (Coulson and Harvey 2013; Hübner, Nückles, and Renkl 2010; Renner et al. 2016). By combining these affordances, mobile technologies can serve as an effective resource for fostering productive teacher education practices and reflective abilities.

The present study

The present study involved a controlled field experiment with pre-service primary and kindergarten teachers using different versions of a mobile portfolio app over the course of a 4-week teaching practice internship in a German-speaking part of Switzerland to foster their reflective abilities and related orientations towards learning to teach. The mobile app 'Metapholio' (www.metapholio.ch) for teacher education was specifically developed for the purpose of this study. The workflow using the app can be described in six steps. 1) Installing the app and creating an account. 2) Inviting fellow pre-service teachers and teacher mentors to view, post, and comment on records and reflections. 3) 'Collecting moments': taking text-based notes, pictures, or recording audio and video files during lessons. This can be done either by the pre-service teachers themselves or by invited peers and mentors. 4) 'Reflecting on moments': Selecting several moments and writing or speaking a reflection on these records. 5) Using moments and reflections as a starting point for comments and discussions between pre-service teachers and invited peers and mentors. 6) Exporting moments, reflections, and interactions for documentation. The core functionality of the app is depicted in [Figure 1](#). A more detailed description of the app is available from Petko et al. (2019).

Different prompts have been integrated within the app to strengthen the connection between theory and practice. When writing reflections, students receive specific prompts (1. Describe what has happened. 2. What was positive? 3. What can be improved? 4. What theories can support you in this regard?). Further, reflections can be attributed to teaching standards and core practices (here, the Interstate Teacher Assessment and Support Consortium [InTASC] standards, [CCSSO 2013](#)).

For the purposes of the present study, pre-service teachers were assigned to two experimental groups to work either with a full version (supporting steps 1–6) or reduced version of the app (supporting steps 1, 2, 4, 5, 6 but not step 3) or a control group that did not work with the app but was required to reflect with a retrospective written report only.

Figure 1. Core functionality of the Metapholio app (from left to right): Collecting moments, a collection of moments, writing a reflection, a written reflection.

By eliminating step 3—the note-taking functionalities with multimedia – the app loses much of its mobile advantages of reflecting-in-action and it is reduced to the functionality of a standard weblog. As such, we compared reflection under three conditions of use: the app with all functionalities, the app as a standard traditional weblog, and without the app.

We investigated the effects of the two treatment conditions and the control condition on pre-service teacher' reflective ability and their orientations towards learning to teach during their internships. The outcomes were particularly examined with regard to the connection between theory and practice, the search for independent information, developing new ideas through discussion, and the proactive use of the mentor during the internship.

Hypotheses

H1: Students using the full version of the app will show more positive development of self-reported reflective abilities than the control group (H1a) or students working with the reduced version of the app (H1b). Students working with the reduced version of the app will show more positive development than those in the control group (H1c).

H2: Students using the full version of the app will show a more positive development of self-reported orientations to teach than the control group (H2a) or students working with the reduced version of the app (H2b). Students working with the reduced version of the app will show more positive development than those in the control group (H2c).

H3: Orientations towards learning to teach will be a positive predictor (H3a) and will show a positive interaction effect with the use of the app (H3b) with regard to the development of self-reported reflective abilities.

Methods

Ethical statement

Data collection, data protection, and ethical issues of the present study were handled according to the guidelines of the German Society of Educational Research, and all data analyses were conducted based on anonymised data.

Sample and procedure

The sample was recruited in January 2019 and consisted of 83 pre-service teachers from a Swiss university of teacher education. The pre-service teachers' age ranged from 18 years to over 30 years, with 38 pre-service teachers between 18–21 years, 36 between 22–25 years, 10 between 26–30 years, and 3 older than 30 years. All teachers were in their second year of study. In total, 77% of the sample were female, with only 3% having a migration background, which is a typical distribution for pre-service teachers in Switzerland.

All of the study measures were assessed before and after a four-week full-time school internship. This internship is a regular part of the primary teacher education program and takes place between the end of 3rd and the beginning of 4th semester. In this internship, the pre-service teachers are assigned to a class where they take full responsibility for teaching all school subjects five days a week, while the regular form teacher takes on the role of a coach. Typically, there are two pre-service teachers in each class who take turns in teaching. Students also receive an intermediary visit from a university mentor who provides additional support and feedback. At the end of the internship, a practical assessment of student teaching took place. This assessment is an important part of the final examinations of pre-service teachers before obtaining their teaching diploma. As a result, the internship can be considered very important for pre-service teachers.

The pre-service teachers' self-evaluated levels of reflection and their orientations towards teaching were measured using online questionnaires in the week before the start of the internship (pre-test) and at the end of the fourth week (post-test). This allowed us to investigate our hypotheses experimentally, examine changes in students' reflection processes, and evaluate their orientations towards learning to teach over the whole time span of the internship. An a priori power analysis indicated that our sample size was sufficient to detect a medium effect size of $f = .25$ for a within/between interaction in a repeated measures ANOVA with three groups and two measurement points with an $\alpha = .05$ and $1 - \beta = .95$, assuming a correlation of $r = .40$ among repeated measures.

Experimental design

For the whole course of the internship, students were randomly assigned to one of the two experimental treatment groups ('Metapholio' or 'Metapholio light') or to the control group. The groups differed with regard to whether they were instructed to reflect on their internship experiences using a mobile portfolio app with full functionalities ('Metapholio'), a reduced version of this app ('Metapholio light'), or neither of these. All three groups attended a kick-off workshop during which the pre-test was administered. The treatment groups also received instruction on how to work with the app during the internship and ethical guidance about data protection issues when working with the app (e.g. not taking pictures in which pupils are recognisable), and they signed a privacy protection agreement declaring their consent to the determined and explained rules of conduct. During the internship, all students received coaching from their mentoring teachers on a daily basis, together with one visit from the university mentor. The teacher mentors had no access to the students' apps. After finishing the internship, all three groups had to write a final reflection paper. However, to balance the workload between the groups, the two treatment groups were allowed to select and integrate passages from their apps, whereas students in the control group had to write their reflections from scratch based on their personal notes. The two experimental groups, together with their control counterparts, are described in more detail in the following section.

Treatment group 1 (Metapholio): full version of a mobile portfolio with multimedia note-taking functionalities (n = 28)

The students in treatment group 1 worked with the full version of 'Metapholio' available in the app stores (<https://metapholio.ch/>), which was developed for the

Figure 2. Examples of two student portfolios. Left: example from the Metapholio group. Right: example from the Metapholio light group.

purpose of this study and runs on (their) personal mobile devices. The app afforded students the capability to take pictures and record short audio or video clips (max. three minutes) of important moments during instruction, including short written texts with the pictures/audio-/video-files or integrating only the text (max. 140 characters). These students were instructed to use the app on a daily basis and to take notes during their lessons whenever something noteworthy occurred. To avoid confusion among their pupils, the pre-service teachers were instructed to explain to their class that they use their mobile devices as a reflection tool and that this is mandatory for their professional education.

Treatment group 2 (Metapholio light): reduced mobile portfolio without multimedia note-taking functionalities (n = 29)

The students in treatment group 2 also worked with a reduced version of the app called 'Metapholio light', which only allowed them to write text-based reflections, excluding the additional note-taking functions (pictures/audio-/video-based note-taking) of the full app. Again, this group was instructed to use the app on a daily basis and write reflections on special and noteworthy events during their teaching. The difference between G1 and G2 is depicted in Figure 2.

Control group: personal note-taking without technological specifications (n = 26)

The control group received no specific app but was encouraged during the kick-off workshop to take personal notes on a daily basis as preparation for the final reflection paper. As this final paper was graded, the students in the control group were expected to actually take these notes during their internship.

Study measures

For all aspects, we chose to use general measures of self-reported reflective ability and orientations towards learning to teach that were not specifically developed to measure

digital or portfolio-based reflection. This intentional choice avoids the issue that the results may be an artefact of the specificity of the measures.

Reflective ability

Students' ability of reflective thinking was assessed with the Groningen Reflective Ability Scale (GRAS, 23 items, Sample item: 'I want to know why I do what I do') developed by Aukes et al. (2007). The items are assessed through a 5-point Likert rating scale ranging from 1 ('totally disagree') to 5 ('totally agree'). The composite score is computed by a sum score ranging from a minimum of 23 to a maximum of 115. Although this scale was originally developed to measure reflection in medical practice and education, it has been successfully applied in many fields of education and practice. In our study, the scale showed good reliability in the pre-test as well as in the post-test (pre-test Cronbach's alpha = .719/McDonald's omega = .761, post-test alpha = .715/omega = .786).

Orientations Toward Learning to Teach were assessed by the scales developed by Oosterheert, Vermunt, and Denessen (2002). In particular, we focus on the subscales addressing learning activities: Proactive broad use of the mentor (6 items, sample item: 'I ask my mentor teacher why according to her/him something in my lesson went in that particular way'), Developing ideas through discussion (5 items, sample item: 'I develop my ideas about education through discussion with experienced teachers in my training school'), Actively relating theory and practice (6 items, sample item 'The way I now want to teach is the result of constantly linking theory to my teaching experience'). All of these scales were assessed on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 ('disagree') to 5 ('agree'). The composite score for each scale is computed with a mean score ranging from 1–5. In our study, the inventory was reliable in three subscales: Proactive Broad Use of the Mentor (6 items; pre-test Cronbach's alpha = .701/McDonald's omega = .710, post-test alpha = .859/omega = .864), Developing Ideas through Discussion (5 items; pre-test alpha = .724/omega = .735, post-test alpha = .834/omega = .840) and Actively Relating Theory and Practice (6 items; pre-test alpha = .797/omega = .798, post-test alpha = .878/omega = .879). The fourth subscale of this inventory, 'Pupil-Oriented Evaluation Criteria', was not found to be reliable (3 items; pre-test alpha = .453/omega = .466, post-test alpha = .537/omega = .647) and was thus excluded from the analysis.

Data analysis

After checking the assumption of homogeneity of variance, we used repeated measures ANOVA to test H1 and H2. To test H3, we used Pearson correlations and linear regression analysis. All analyses were conducted in Jamovi (2.2.5). Due to the online administration of the questionnaires, the dataset did not include any missing data.

Results

Descriptive estimated marginal means for all group comparisons can be found in Table 1.

The development of the estimated marginal means of the self-reported *Reflective Ability* of the two treatment groups and the control group is depicted in Figure 3. A repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to test H1. The results showed no between-subject differences for group membership ($F(2,80) = 1.40, p = .252, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .034$).

Table 1. Mean scores (M) and standard deviations (SD) of estimated marginal means for the treatment groups and the control group in the pre-test and the post-test regarding reflective activity and orientations towards learning to teach.

Group	Time	Reflective Ability	Proactive Use of the Mentor	Developing Ideas Through Discussion	Actively Relating Theory and Practice
METAPHOLIO	pre	90.9 (1.40)	4.13 (0.08)	3.43 (0.12)	3.41 (0.12)
	post	95.2 (1.37)	4.39 (0.12)	3.74 (0.15)	3.38 (0.16)
METAPHOLIO LIGHT	pre	94.1 (1.38)	4.02 (0.08)	3.43 (0.12)	3.46 (0.12)
	post	95.1 (1.35)	4.18 (0.12)	3.79 (0.14)	3.09 (0.16)
CONTROL	pre	92.8 (1.45)	4.27 (0.08)	3.58 (0.13)	3.74 (0.13)
	post	94.8 (1.42)	4.21 (0.12)	3.5 (0.15)	3.43 (0.17)

Figure 3. Self-reported reflective ability across treatment groups over time.

Regarding within-subject effects, we found a marginally significant main effect for the development of reflective ability over time ($F(1,80) = 3.89, p = .052, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .046$) but there were no significant interaction effects when comparing this development between the groups ($F(2,80) = 2.27, p = .110, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .054$). Thus, H1 was rejected. Although there seemed to be a visible tendency in the data that might support our hypothesis, the effects were too small to be significant.

Regarding H2, we analysed the differences between the treatment and the control groups regarding the orientation towards the *Proactive and Broad Use of the Mentor* (Figure 4). The results showed no between-subject effects for group membership ($F(2,80) = 1.01, p = .367, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .025$); however, there was a marginally significant main effect for time within subjects ($F(1,80) = 3.89, p = .052, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .046$). The interaction effect of time*group was non-significant ($F(2,80) = 2.27, p = .110, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .054$), leading to the rejection of H2 for this sub-aspect. There seemed to be a tendency in the data that might support the hypothesis, but the effects were too small to reach significance.

With regard to the orientation towards *Developing Ideas through Discussion*, the results seemed to partially support H2 (Figure 5). Although there was no between-subject effect ($F(2,80) = .094, p = .911, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .002$), there was a significant increase in this orientation over time ($F(1,80) = 7.06, p = .009, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .081$) and a clear difference between groups in this increase ($F(2,80) = 3.32, p = .041, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .038$).

Figure 4. Proactive use of the mentor across treatment groups over time.

Figure 5. Developing ideas through discussion across treatment groups over time.

= .077). Both experimental groups showed a clear increase in their orientation towards developing ideas through discussion, whereas the control group did not. However, as the effects were fairly small, post-hoc tests failed to identify the exact differences between these groups.

With regard to *Actively Relating Theory and Practice* (Figure 6), we found no significant between-subject effect regarding group membership ($F(2,80) = .094, p = .911$, partial $\eta^2 = .002$), but a significant within-subject effect for time ($F(1,80) = 12.68, p = .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .137$) and a marginally significant interaction effect for time*group ($F(2,80) = 2.41, p = .096$, partial $\eta^2 = .057$). Examining the descriptive statistics, it is evident that this orientation decreased in the control group and the Metapholio Light group, whereas it remained roughly the same in the group that worked with the full version of the app.

The correlation of the different variables (Table 2) revealed that post-test *Reflective Ability* was not only strongly correlated with pre-test *Reflective Ability* but also with the

Figure 6. Actively relating theory and practice across treatment groups over time.

Table 2. Correlation matrix of reflective ability (pre-test and post-test) and orientations learning towards teaching (post-test).

	Reflective Ability Pre	Reflective Ability Post	Proactive Use of the Mentor post	Developing ideas through Discussion post	Relating Theory and Practice post
Reflective Ability pre	—				
Reflective Ability post	0.549***	—			
Proactive Use of the Mentor post	0.162	0.488***	—		
Developing ideas through Discussion post	0.219*	0.306**	0.414***	—	
Relating Theory and Practice post	0.053	0.235*	0.317**	0.413***	—

Proactive use of the Mentor, Developing Ideas Through Discussion, and, to a lesser extent, Relating Theory and Practice.

To test H3 and to factor in the comparison of the treatment groups, we conducted a linear regression analysis with post-test *Reflective Ability* as the dependent variable. In the model, we included all variables of the correlation analysis as well as dummy-coded group membership, with the control group as the reference category. Table 3 shows that post-test *Reflective Ability* can be predicted by pre-test *Reflective Ability* and the *Proactive*

Table 3. Regression analysis predicting posttest reflective ability through pretest reflective ability, orientations to learning to teach, and group membership.

Predictors	Estimate	SE	t	p
Intercept ^a	30.1907	8.1937	3.6846	<.001
Reflective Ability Pretest	0.4703	0.0843	5.5774	<.001
Proactive Use of the Mentor Posttest	4.3296	1.0947	3.9552	<.001
Developing Ideas Through Discussion Posttest	0.0675	0.9441	0.0715	0.943
Actively Relating Theory and Practice Posttest	0.7217	0.8081	0.8930	0.375
group:				
METAPHOLIO LIGHT – CONTROL	0.0344	1.5311	0.0225	0.982
METAPHOLIO – CONTROL	0.5371	1.5117	0.3553	0.723

^aRepresents reference level.

Table 4. Regression analysis predicting posttest reflective ability through pretest reflective ability, proactive use of the mentor, and the interaction with using the mobile portfolio app.

Predictors	Estimate	SE	t	p
Intercept ^a	31.3648	8.0341	3.904	<.001
Reflective Ability Pretest	0.4708	0.0823	5.718	<.001
Proactive Use of the Mentor Posttest	4.6925	1.0136	4.630	<.001
Proactive Use of the Mentor Post * group:				
Mentor * (METAPHOLIO LIGHT – CONTROL)	–0.0404	0.3425	–0.118	0.906
Mentor * (METAPHOLIO – CONTROL)	0.0777	0.3416	0.227	0.821

^aRepresents reference level.

Use of the Mentor. Other variables did not provide further explanatory effects. The model explained 47.3% of the variance in the dependent variable. By including only the significant predictors, this dropped only marginally to 46.5%.

To test the interaction effect of the use of the app and the *Proactive Use of the Mentor*, we computed an additional regression model, as summarised in Table 4.

The results of this regression analysis showed that H3a can be partially accepted, whereas H3b and H3c were rejected. Although the *Proactive Use of the Mentor* was clearly related to the development of self-reported reflective ability of pre-service teachers during their teaching internship, the use of a mobile portfolio app did not seem to enhance this positive effect in a significant way.

Discussion

Our experimental study examined the effects of using different variants of a mobile portfolio app on pre-service teachers' self-reported reflective ability and orientations towards learning to teach. Furthermore, we investigated the effects of the students' orientations on reflective abilities across different uses of the mobile portfolio app. With regard to our hypothesis that a mobile portfolio app might positively influence the development of pre-service teachers' reflective ability over the course of a teaching internship, we found no advantages of using either variant of the mobile portfolio app in comparison to the control group. With regard to their orientations towards teaching, the mobile portfolio app had a significant and positive influence on their orientation towards developing new ideas through discussion. However, post-hoc tests could not reveal significant differences between subgroups. There were additional small and marginally significant effects with regard to proactively engaging the mentor during internships. This leads to the impression that the use of the mobile portfolio app could have a positive influence on the social processes related to reflection. The test of the interplay of the different factors made it apparent that both the orientation towards developing ideas through discussion and proactively engaging the mentor were positively related to reflective ability, as was the orientation towards actively relating theory and practice. However, the use of the mobile portfolio app did not seem to enhance this relationship, as shown in the regression analysis. Consequently, H1 could be clearly rejected, and H2 and H3 were only partially confirmed. This leads to the impression that there might be indirect rather than direct effects of using mobile portfolio apps to support teacher reflection. In this study, we found surprisingly few clear indicators that the full version of the app, which includes multimedia note-taking functionalities, was more beneficial than the reduced

version with regard to the development of self-reported reflective ability and orientations towards learning to teach. This is even more surprising as the app version with multimedia functionality was met with higher levels of technology acceptance (Petko et al. 2023). One reason for the lack of findings might be the rather superficial integration of the app into the teaching internship in which the use of the app was mandatory; however, we did not exactly prescribe how it should be used. As in other studies on reflective writing, teacher education studies might benefit from stronger scaffolding and feedback when using these kinds of applications (Coulson and Harvey 2013; Hübner, Nückles, and Renkl 2010; Renner et al. 2016). This has been supported by a recent in-depth analysis of the mentor-student-interactions when using this app (Michos and Petko 2024). Nevertheless, our findings are in line with previous research on digital portfolios, highlighting the affordances of their collaborative use in teacher education contexts (Adadan and Oner 2018; Dune et al. 2018; Kelly 2010; Kloser et al. 2021; Michos et al. 2022). The literature also emphasises the specific affordances of mobile technologies that can provide a stronger link between noticing-in-action and reflection-on-action (Baran 2014; Garcia-Martinez et al. 2019; Leinonen et al. 2014; Seppälä and Alamäki 2003). In addition, digital portfolios could become commonplace with new generations of prospective teachers who are used to social media (Petko et al. 2023). It would not be surprising if traditional paper & pencil portfolios were soon to be a thing of the past.

Limitations of the study, implications, and future directions

A first limitation of the study is the fact that the effects of the mobile portfolio app 'Metapholio' together with pre-service teachers' ability to reflect were tested with a sample of primary education and kindergarten pre-service teachers from a single Swiss university of teacher education. Therefore, future studies should include various schools and different school types to enable generalisable predictions regarding pre-service teachers' effects of the app use and their reflection processes. Furthermore, future studies might include more experienced teachers to compare the interplay of teachers' expertise level, their reflective competencies, and the effects of using a reflective app. Theoretical considerations, especially from Berliner (1988), point to important differences between inexperienced (novices) and more experienced (experts) teachers concerning '[...] interpreting classroom phenomena; [...] discerning the importance of events; [...] using routines; [...] predicting classroom phenomena; [...] judging typical and atypical events; and [...] evaluating performance'. Hence, expert teachers can reflect on their behaviour on a much richer knowledge base and might therefore especially profit from using the app, as they presumably already have a very high level of reflective competency at their disposal.

Another point to consider is that we assessed all the variables using self-reported questionnaires. The psychometric qualities of the scales used in this study were adequate; self-reports have been shown to be strongly affected by subjective beliefs (e.g. Robinson and Clore 2002). Hence, future studies should attempt to triangulate data of pre-service teachers' instructional quality to corroborate the results of this study. Another limitation of the study is the relatively short time span of four weeks in assessing the fundamental effects of improvement on reflective abilities.

Despite these limitations, our study has numerous fundamental strengths. First, we developed a mobile portfolio app that was specifically constructed to strengthen the reflective processes of pre-service teachers during their teaching practice. Second, we followed teacher students using a full-app version, a reduced version of the app, and a control group over a 4-week period during their first practical teaching experiences classroom. Although the app did not lead to significant direct effects with regard to the development of reflective abilities, it might be seen as a social tool that might strengthen the interaction between students and mentors and that might serve as a focus to develop ideas through discussion.

Practical implications

Practical implications of the results of our study include the need to support pre-service teachers in reflecting on their classroom practices, as reflection was important for their instructional quality. Future intervention studies could build on the results of our study by implementing mobile portfolio apps with an even more thorough design of reflection tasks and social interactions. First, pre-service teachers should be supported in using the app in a social way, which refers to receiving prompts that elicit interaction with others when reflecting on the experiences collected within the app. A more refined design of the social interactions when using the app for relevant student teachers' activities might lead to more benefits with regard to reflective activities. Second, scaffolding in its original meaning – fading out of experts' support – might be useful in such a way that more support from the regular form teachers and the university mentors working with the app might be needed at the beginning of the pre-service teachers' internship to reduce extraneous cognitive load (Sharma and Hannafin 2007; Sweller, van Merriënboer, and Paas 1998). Third, feedback from experienced teachers to novice ones has already been proven effective when it is specific, positive, and/or corrective (for a review study, see Scheeler, Ruhl, and McAfee 2004). Hence, feedback from both the experienced teachers and the university mentors regarding pre-service teachers' reflection process and how to improve their classroom behaviour might additionally enhance the positive effects of mobile portfolio apps for improving pre-service teachers' instructional quality.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

This research project was funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation [Grant Number 100019_173049].

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References

- Adadan, E., and D. Oner. 2018. "Examining Preservice teachers' Reflective Thinking Skills in the Context of Web-Based Portfolios: The Role of Metacognitive Awareness." *Australian Journal of Teacher Education (Online)* 43 (11): 26–50. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2018v43n11.2>.
- Archambault, L., K. Wetzel, T. S. Foulger, and M. K. Williams. 2010. "Professional Development 2.0: Transforming Teacher Education Pedagogy with 21st Century Tools." *Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education* 27 (1): 4–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21532974.2010.10784651>.
- Aukes, L. C., J. Geertsma, J. Cohen-Schotanus, R. P. Zwierstra, and J. P. Slaets. 2007. "The Development of a Scale to Measure Personal Reflection in Medical Practice and Education." *Medical Teacher* 29 (2–3): 177–182. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590701299272>.
- Bakkenes, I., J. D. Vermunt, and T. Wubbels. 2010. "Teacher Learning in the Context of Educational Innovation: Learning Activities and Learning Outcomes of Experienced Teachers." *Learning & Instruction* 20 (6): 533–548. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2009.09.001>.
- Baran, E. 2014. "A Review of Research on Mobile Learning in Teacher Education." *Educational Technology & Society* 17:17–32. www.jstor.org/stable/jeductechsoci.17.4.17.
- Beauchamp, C. 2015. "Reflection in Teacher Education: Issues Emerging from a Review of Current Literature." *Reflective Practice* 16 (1): 123–141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14623943.2014.982525>.
- Berliner, D. C. 1988. *The Development of Expertise in Pedagogy*. AACTE Publications. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED298122.pdf>.
- Blömeke, S., A. Felbrich, C. Müller, G. Kaiser, and R. Lehmann. 2008. "Effectiveness of Teacher Education." *International Journal on Mathematics Education* 40 (5): 719–734. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-008-0096-x>.
- Blömeke, S., J.-E. Gustafsson, and R. Shavelson. 2015. "Beyond Dichotomies: Competence Viewed as a Continuum." *Zeitschrift für Psychologie* 223 (1): 3–13. <https://doi.org/10.1027/2151-2604/a000194>.
- Burn, K., and T. Mutton. 2015. "A Review of 'Research-Informed Clinical practice' in Initial Teacher Education." *Oxford Review of Education* 41 (2): 217–233. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2015.1020104>.
- Cohen, E., R. Hoz, and H. Kaplan. 2013. "The Practicum in Preservice Teacher Education: A Review of Empirical Studies." *Teaching Education* 24 (4): 345–380. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10476210.2012.711815>.
- Coulson, D., and M. Harvey. 2013. "Scaffolding Student Reflection for Experience-Based Learning: A Framework." *Teaching in Higher Education* 18 (4): 401–413. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2012.752726>.

- Council of Chief State School Officers. 2013. "InTASC Model Core Teaching Standards and Learning Progressions for Teachers 1.0: A Resource for Ongoing Teacher Development." CCSSO. Accessed by July 19, 2021 from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED558115.pdf>.
- Darling-Hammond, L., and N. Richardson. 2009. "Teacher Learning: What Matters." *Educational Leadership* 66 (5): 46–53.
- Depaepe, F., L. Verschaffel, and J. Star. 2020. "Expertise in Developing students' Expertise in Mathematics: Bridging teachers' Professional Knowledge and Instructional Quality." *International Journal on Mathematics Education* 52 (2): 179–192. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-020-01148-8>.
- Dewey, J. 1904. "The Relation of Theory to Practice in Education." In *The Relation Between Theory and Practice in the Education of Teachers: Third Yearbook of the National Society for the Scientific Study of Education, Part 1*, edited by C. A. McMurry, 9–30. Chicago, IL: The University of Chicago Press.
- Dickey, M. D. 2004. "The Impact of Weblogs (Blogs) on Student Perceptions of Isolation and Alienation in a Web-Based Distance-Learning Environment." *Open Learning: The Journal of Open, Distance and E-Learning* 19 (3): 279–291. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0268051042000280138>.
- Dune, T., K. Crnek-Georgeson, J. Bidewell, R. Firdaus, J. R. John, and A. Arora. 2018. "Undergraduate Health Science students' Development of Reflective Practice on Communication Skills via E-Portfolios." *Journal of University Teaching & Learning Practice* 15 (3): 5. <https://doi.org/10.53761/1.15.3.5>.
- Dyment, J. E., and T. S. O'Connell. 2010. "The Quality of Reflection in Student Journals: A Review of Limiting and Enabling Factors." *Innovative Higher Education* 35 (4): 233–244. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10755-010-9143-y>.
- Ebner, M., C. Lienhardt, M. Rohs, and I. Meyer. 2010. "Microblogs in Higher Education – a Chance to Facilitate Informal and Process-Oriented Learning?" *Computers & Education* 55 (1): 92–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2009.12.006>.
- Endedijk, M. D., V. Donche, and I. Oosterheert. 2013. "Student teachers' Learning Patterns in School-Based Teacher Education Programmes: The Influence of Person, Context and Time." In *Learning Patterns in Higher Education: Dimensions and Research Perspectives*, edited by D. Gijbels, V. Donche, J. T. E. Richardson, and J. D. Vermunt, 102–122. London, UK: Routledge.
- Feder, L., and C. Cramer. 2019. "Portfolioarbeit in der Lehrerbildung. Ein systematischer Forschungsüberblick [Portfolio in teacher education. A research synthesis]." *Zeitschrift für Erziehungswissenschaft* 22 (5): 1225–1245. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11618-019-00903-2>.
- Fendler, L. 2003. "Teacher Reflection in a Hall of Mirrors: Historical Influences and Political Reverberations." *Educational Researcher* 32 (3): 16–25. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X032003016>.
- Garcia-Martinez, I., J. M. Fernandez-Batanero, D. C. Sanchiz, and A. L. de la Rosa. 2019. "Using Mobile Devices for Improving Learning Outcomes and teachers' Professionalization." *Sustainability* 11 (24): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11246917>.
- Gaudin, C., and S. Chaliès. 2015. "Video Viewing in Teacher Education and Professional Development: A Literature Review." *Educational Research Review* 16:41–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2015.06.001>.
- Goller, M., C. Harteis, D. Gijbels, and V. Donche. 2020. "Engineering students' Learning During Internships: Exploring the Explanatory Power of the Job Demands-Control-Support Model." *Journal of Engineering Education* 109 (2): 307–324. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jee.20308>.
- Goodwin, C. 1994. "Professional Vision." *American Anthropologist* 96 (3): 606–633. <https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.1994.96.3.02a00100>.
- Greenhow, C., D. Campbell, S. Galvin, and E. Askari. 2018. "Social Media in Teacher Professional Development: A Literature Review." *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology and Teacher Education International Conference 2018*, edited by E. Langran and J. Borup, 2256–2264. Washington, DC: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education.
- Hadjistassou, S. K., and C. Allen. 2018. "Using iPad-Mediated Recordings to Offer Contingent Feedback and Introduce Pre-Service Teachers to the Epistemology of the Teaching Practice." *Journal of Computers in Education* 5 (3): 373–392. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-018-0110-4>.

- Hamel, C., A. Viau-Guay, and B. Nkuyubwatsi. 2019. "Using Video to Support teachers' Reflective Practice: A Literature Review." *Cogent Education* 6 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2019.1673689>.
- Hascher, T. 2012. "Learning Setting Student Teaching—Evidence Based Developments in Teacher Education." *Zeitschrift Für Bildungsforschung* 2 (2): 109–129. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s35834-012-0032-6>.
- Hiebert, J. 1999. "Relationships Between Research and the NCTM Standards." *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education* 30 (1): 3–19. <https://doi.org/10.2307/749627>.
- Hramiak, A., H. Boulton, and B. Irwin. 2009. "Trainee Teachers' use of Blogs as Private Reflections for Professional Development." *Learning, Media and Technology* 34 (3): 259–269. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439880903141521>.
- Hübner, S., M. Nückles, and A. Renkl. 2010. "Writing Learning Journals: Instructional Support to Overcome Learning-Strategy Deficits." *Learning & Instruction* 20 (1): 18–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2008.12.001>.
- Iredale, A., K. Stapleford, D. Tremayne, L. Farrell, C. Holbrey, and J. Sheridan-Ross. 2019. "A Review and Synthesis of the use of Social Media in Initial Teacher Education." *Technology, Pedagogy & Education* 29 (1): 19–34. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1475939X.2019.1693422>.
- Karsenti, T., G. Dumouchel, and S. Collin. 2014. "The Eportfolio as Support for the Professional Development of Preservice Teachers: A Theoretical and Practical Overview." *International Journal of Computers & Technology* 12 (5): 3486–3495. <https://doi.org/10.24297/ijct.v12i5.2919>.
- Kelly, M. 2010. "Professional Pedagogies and Research Practices: Teaching and Researching Reflective Inquiry Through a Medical Portfolio Process." In *Handbook of Reflection and Reflective Inquiry*, edited by N. Lyons, 351–381. Boston, MA: Springer.
- Kloser, M., A. Edelman, C. Floyd, J. F. Martinez, B. Stecher, J. Srinivasan, and E. Lavin. 2021. "Interrogating Practice or Show and Tell?: Using a Digital Portfolio to Anchor a Professional Learning Community of Science Teachers." *Journal of Science Teacher Education* 32 (2): 210–241. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1046560X.2020.1808267>.
- Kori, K., M. Pedaste, Å. Leijen, and M. Mäeots. 2014. "Supporting Reflection in Technology-Enhanced Learning." *Educational Research Review* 11:45–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2013.11.003>.
- Korthagen, F. A. J., and J. P. Kessels. 1999. "Linking Theory and Practice: Changing the Pedagogy of Teacher Education." *Educational Researcher* 28 (4): 4–17. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X028004004>.
- Korthagen, F. A. J., J. Loughran, and T. Russell. 2006. "Developing Fundamental Principles for Teacher Education Programs and Practices." *Teaching & Teacher Education* 22 (8): 1020–1041. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2006.04.022>.
- Krutka, D. G., D. J. Bergman, R. Flores, K. Mason, and A. R. Jack. 2014. "Microblogging About Teaching: Nurturing Participatory Cultures Through Collaborative Online Reflection with Pre-Service Teachers." *Teaching & Teacher Education* 40:83–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2014.02.002>.
- Lachner, A., H. Jarodzka, and M. Nückles. 2016. "What Makes an Expert Teacher? Investigating teachers' Professional Vision and Discourse Abilities." *Instructional Science* 44 (3): 197–203. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11251-016-9376-y>.
- Leinonen, T., A. Keune, M. Veermans, and T. Toikkanen. 2014. "Mobile Apps for Reflection in Learning: A Design Research in K-12 Education." *British Journal of Educational Technology* 47 (1): 184–202. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12224>.
- Lipowski, F. 2011. "Theoretische Perspektiven und empirische Befunde zur Wirksamkeit von Lehrerfort- und Weiterbildung" [Theoretical Perspectives and Empirical Results of the Effectiveness of Advanced Trainings for Teachers]. In *Handbuch der Forschung zum Lehrberuf* [Handbook of research of the teaching profession], edited by E. Terhart, H. Bennewitz, and M. Rothland, 398–417. Münster: Waxmann.
- Lyons, N. 2010. "Reflection and Reflective Inquiry: Critical Issues, Evolving Conceptualization, Contemporary Claims and Future Possibilities." In *Handbook of Reflection and Reflective Inquiry. Mapping a Way of Knowing for Professional Reflective Inquiry*, edited by N. Lyons, 3–22. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-85744-2_1.

- Maksimović, J., and J. Osmanović. 2018. "Reflective Practice as a Changing Factor of Teaching Quality." *Research in Pedagogy* 8 (2): 172–189. <https://doi.org/10.17810/2015.82>.
- Marcos, J. J. M., E. S. Miguel, and H. Tillema. 2009. "Teacher Reflection on Action: What is Said (In Research) and What is Done (In Teaching)." *Reflective Practice* 10 (2): 191–204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14623940902786206>.
- Michos, K., A. Cantieni, R. Schmid, L. Müller, and D. Petko. 2022. "Examining the Relationship Between Internship Experiences, Teaching Enthusiasm, and Teacher Self-Efficacy When using a Mobile Portfolio App." *Teaching & Teacher Education* 109:103570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103570>.
- Michos, K., and D. Petko. 2024. "Reflection using Mobile Portfolios During Teaching Internships: Tracing the Influence of Mentors and Peers on Teacher Self-Efficacy." *Technology, Pedagogy & Education* 33 (3): 291–311. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1475939X.2024.2311798>.
- Moon, J. A. 1999. "Reflection in Learning and Professional Development". *Theory and Practice*. London: Kogan Page. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203822296>.
- Moon, J. A. 2006. *Learning Journals: A Handbook for Reflective Practice and Professional Development*. London: Routledge.
- Oosterheert, I. E., J. D. Vermunt, and E. J. P. G. Denessen. 2002. "Assessing Orientations to Learning to Teach." *The British Journal of Educational Psychology* 72 (1): 41–64. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709902158766>.
- Petko, D., A. Cantieni, R. Schmid, L. Müller, M. Krannich, and K. Michos. 2023. "Technology Acceptance of a Mobile Portfolio App for Teacher Education: Pre-Service Teachers Views on Multimedia-Based Note-Taking and Mentoring in Internships." *Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education* 39 (1): 57–71. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21532974.2022.2142990>.
- Petko, D., N. Egger, and A. Cantieni. 2017. "Weblogs in Teacher Education Internships: Promoting Reflection and Self-Efficacy While Reducing Stress?" *Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education* 33 (2): 78–87. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21532974.2017.1280434>.
- Petko, D., R. Schmid, L. Müller, and M. Hielscher. 2019. "Metapholio: A Mobile App for Supporting Collaborative Note Taking and Reflection in Teacher Education." *Technology, Knowledge, and Learning* 24 (4): 699–710. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10758-019-09398-6>.
- Prestridge, S. 2019. "Categorising teachers' use of Social Media for their Professional Learning: A Self-Generating Professional Learning Paradigm." *Computers & Education* 129:143–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.11.003>.
- Prilop, C. N., K. E. Weber, and M. Kleinknecht. 2019. "How Digital Reflection and Feedback Environments Contribute to Pre-Service teachers' Beliefs During a Teaching Practicum." *Studies in Educational Evaluation* 62:158–170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2019.06.005>.
- Renner, B., M. Prilla, U. Cress, and J. Kimmerle. 2016. "Effects of Prompting in Reflective Learning Tools: Findings from Experimental Field, Lab, and Online Studies." *Frontiers in Psychology* 7:820. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00820>.
- Robinson, M. D., and G. L. Clore. 2002. "Belief and Feeling: Evidence for an Accessibility Model of Emotional Self-Report." *Psychological Bulletin* 128 (6): 934–960. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.128.6.934>.
- Roessger, K. M. 2014. "The Effect of Reflective Activities on Instrumental Learning in Adult Work-Related Education: A Critical Review of the Empirical Research." *Educational Research Review* 13:17–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2014.06.002>.
- Roffey-Barentsen, J., and R. Malthouse. 2009. *Reflective Practice in the Lifelong Learning Sector*. Exeter: Sage.
- Romano, M., and J. Schwartz. 2005. "Exploring Technology as a Tool for Eliciting and Encouraging Beginning Teacher Reflection." *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education* 5 (2): 149–168.
- Scheeler, M. C., K. L. Ruhl, and J. K. McAfee. 2004. "Providing Performance Feedback to Teachers: A Review." *Teacher Education and Special Education* 27 (4): 396–407. <https://doi.org/10.1177/088840640402700407>.
- Schön, D. A. 1983. *The Reflective Practitioner: How Professionals Think in Action*. New York: Basic Books.

- Schüpbach, J. 2007. *Über das Unterrichten reden. Die Unterrichtsnachbesprechung in den Lehrpraktika – Eine "Nahtstelle von Theorie und Praxis"?* [Talking about teaching. Debriefing of teaching during school internships – Connecting theory and practice?]. Bern: Haupt.
- Seidel, T., and K. Stürmer. 2014. "Modeling and Measuring the Structure of Professional Vision in Preservice Teachers." *American Educational Research Journal* 51 (4): 739–771. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831214531321>.
- Seppälä, P., and H. Alamäki. 2003. "Mobile Learning in Teacher Training." *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning* 19 (3): 330–335. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.0266-4909.2003.00034.x>.
- Sharma, P., and M. J. Hannafin. 2007. "Scaffolding in Technology Enhanced Learning Environments." *Interactive Learning Environments* 15 (1): 27–46. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820600996972>.
- Shulman, L. S. 1998. "Theory, Practice, and the Education of Professionals." *The Elementary School Journal* 98 (5): 511–526. <https://doi.org/10.1086/461912>.
- Sim, J. W. S., and K. F. Hew. 2010. "The use of Weblogs in Higher Education Settings: A Review of Empirical Research." *Educational Research Review* 5 (2): 151–163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2010.01.001>.
- Sophonhiranrak, S. 2021. "Features, Barriers, and Influencing Factors of Mobile Learning in Higher Education: A Systematic Review." *Heliyon* 7 (4): e06696. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06696>.
- Strudler, N., and K. Wetzel. 2005. "The Diffusion of Electronic Portfolios in Teacher Education: Issues of Initiation and Implementation." *Journal of Research on Technology in Education* 37 (4): 411–433. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2005.10782446>.
- Sweller, J., J. J. van Merriënboer, and F. G. Paas. 1998. "Cognitive Architecture and Instructional Design." *Educational Psychology Review* 10 (3): 251–296. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1022193728205>.
- Top, E., E. Yukselturk, and F. A. Inan. 2010. "Reconsidering usage of Blogging in Preservice Teacher Education Courses." *The Internet and Higher Education* 13 (4): 214–217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2010.05.003>.
- van Beveren, L., G. Roets, A. Buisse, and K. Rutten. 2018. "We All Reflect, but Why? A Systematic Review of the Purposes of Reflection in Higher Education in Social and Behavioral Sciences." *Educational Research Review* 24:1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2018.01.002>.
- Wideen, M., J. Mayer-Smith, and B. Moon. 1998. "A Critical Analysis of the Research on Learning to Teach: Making the Case for an Ecological Perspective on Inquiry." *Review of Educational Research* 68 (2): 130–178. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543068002130>.
- Wopereis, I. G. J. H., P. B. Sloep, and S. H. Poortman. 2010. "Weblogs as Instruments for Reflection on Action in Teacher Education." *Interactive Learning Environments* 18 (3): 245–261. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2010.500530>.
- Wright, N. 2010. "Twittering in Teacher Education: Reflecting on Practicum Experiences." *Open Learning: The Journal of Open, Distance and E-Learning* 25 (3): 259–265. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680513.2010.512102>.
- Zeichner, K. M. 1987. "Preparing Reflective Teachers: An Overview of Instructional Strategies which Have Been Employed in Preservice Teacher Education." *International Journal of Educational Research* 11 (5): 565–575. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0883-0355\(87\)90016-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0883-0355(87)90016-4).
- Zeichner, K. M., and B. R. Tabachnick. 1981. "Are the Effects of University Teacher Education 'Washed out' by School Experience?" *Journal of Teacher Education* 32 (3): 7–11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002248718103200302>.